

Survey on the Status of Rainwater Garnering Structure Implementation and its Suitability for Insertion: A case study at K V Kandrika, Pathapadu, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract

Rainwater harvesting (RwH) is a venerable method, known for tapping the rainwater to address the depleting ground water resources. Assimilating the rain where it falls, or netting the run-off is defined as water harvesting and, innumerable forms of water harvesting techniques have been espoused traditionally over the centuries. The current generation is witnessing rapid globalization aided with industrialization, which indeed coupled with short and uneven rainfall is tiling a way for the reduction in surface water levels. Consequently, this is resulting in the dependence on ground water on a large scale over the past decades, instigating a steep fall in the ground water levels. In this study, a survey was carried out at K V Kandrika, Pathapadu, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh, India on to figure out the status of rainwater garnering structure (RwGS) implementation and study the suitability for its insertion. A simple design of rainwater recharge pit was proposed for diverting the rainwater from rooftop of a selected house in the community and M. P. U. P School premises at K V Kandrika, Pathapadu, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh, India. This may perhaps aid in tapping the rainwater where it falls and when it falls.

Keywords: Rainwater garnering structure, Ground water table, Rainfall, Harvesting, Recharge

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1. Introduction

It is an unprecedented fact that water is one among the five basic principle elements for the existence of life on the planet earth and certainly, it plays a commendable role in the progress of communities that include economic and social activities (1). It is a known fact that rainwater harvesting (RwH) technique is an age-old practice immensely known in many countries; however, designing the volume of the storage tank for collecting the rooftop rainwater has always been a puzzling task. It is well cited in the literature that the rooftop rainwater harvesting technique would prove operative in the regions with heavy rainfall intensity and with well-distributed rainfall over the years (2). The RwH technique is deliberated as one of the substitute for drinking water in most of the coastal areas and areas affected by arsenic, where the sources of surface and groundwater are limited, otherwise, the water supply which is existing is insufficient to meet the regular water demand (3, 4). There is an increasing demand in promoting rooftop RwH at the household and community level to address the condition of lacking an improved water supply (5). Individual houses or communities, the private and public schools, colleges, institutions and government offices would rather become a driving force to implement the RwH systems owing to the vast rooftop area available, and therefore, would be effective in tapping the rainwater effectively (6). This is the oldest and simplest method for self-supply of water in residential areas. It can also be adopted for offices, institutions, hospitals, and other organizations.

India has an ancient tradition in the enactment of rainwater harvesting structures. Nevertheless, the tradition, and the knowledge and management systems that complemented it have been diluted owing to few changes, largely accounted by colonial attitudes to water management and administration. Perhaps, rainwater harvesting structures in the past resulted in becoming the major provider of water, replacing communities and households as the primary units for provision and management of water. Furthermore, the other is the growing emphasis on the use of surface and groundwater, while the earlier dependence on rainwater and floodwater has waned, even though rainwater and floodwater are available in plenty (7). A study conducted by Schewe et al. (8) reported an unfavorable impact of climate change on water scarcity and sensed that there is a need to address this growing world water issues.

As a matter of positive note, the recent initiatives put forward by both the community and governments prove that stimulating rainwater garnering structures (RwGS) can intensely

restore ecosystems and contribute to development. Nevertheless, the success of these instances merely not just depend on putting into practice of the RwGS; the entire exercise must be strengthened by community-based decision making systems, institutions, and facilitating legal and financial measures which endorse community action. The central government of India has taken up a recent initiative for tapping the rainwater, i.e., Jal Shakti Abhiyan- Catch the Rain (JSA-CTR) with the theme catch the rain, where it falls, when it falls. The initiative mainly aims at water conservation and rainwater harvesting, renovation of traditional and other water bodies/ tanks, reuse and recharge of bore wells, watershed development and intensive afforestation (9).

Several types of RwH system configurations are prevailing, which are already in practice. Some systems are communal, usually formed as tank collecting water from a large roof area and supplying it to a number of residence areas, whereas other systems are installed on individual houses (10). Large-scale implementation of RwH systems is possible and would become a game changer with single managing system, sufficient financial assistance and large roof top area. Nevertheless, limited information is available on the reports addressing the implementation of RwH in residences, schools, colleges, government buildings, universities/institutes, etc. (11). The sustainable development goals (SDGs) 6 and 12 laid emphasis on supporting the communities with clean water, sanitation and on responsible consumption and production. In achieving this, there is a need to readdress and aim at developing new designs for tapping the rainwater where it falls and when it falls, and assure its implementation in urban and rural areas on a large-scale, which subsequently aids in recharging and, maintain ground water balance to make it a sustainable source of life.

Therefore, in this study, an effort was made to carry out an initial field survey to collect data on the status of RwGS implementation pertaining to K V Kandrika, Pathapadu, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh, India. The survey was carried out in 40 houses and one government school, covering a total of nearly 200 individuals and 20 students belonging to eighth and ninth class, respectively. A questionnaire was devised comprising of questions covering both the general and technical information sufficient to understand the state of mind of the community. The interaction with the community was carried out with the aid of the questionnaire prepared. The survey results provided valuable insights into the socio-economic conditions of the community, subsequently; the study was aimed at developing a location specific design and implementing the same.

2. Materials and methodology

Study area

The selected study area is K V Kandrika, located at Pathapadu village, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh State, India. Figure 1 shows the satellite image of the study area highlighted in red circle with 16.58°N and 80.66°E. The meteorological data of the study area is listed in Table 1.

Figure 1. Satellite image of the study area highlighted in red circle

Table 1. Meteorological data of the study area district.

Parameter	Average value
Average rainfall	(1011.2 to 1013.1) mm
Humidity	70-80%
Temperature	23.4–40 °C (74–104 °F)
Wind	5.9 -10.3 miles per hour
Earthquake zone	Zone III
Elevation / Altitude	24 meters

Methodology

Initially, the project was planned to survey selected number of houses within the vicinity of the selected community. Simultaneously, the study was also aimed at surveying few schools for awareness on the selected topic among the students who are the ambassadors of the future. The survey was carried out using a questionnaire comprising of questions covering both the general and technical information sufficient to understand the state of mind of the community. The data collected from both the community and schools was uploaded to Google form for data analysis. The soil across the selected study area is of red and black soil with highly undulated ground surfaces. The ground water wells and water provided by the local Municipal corporation works serve as source of water for all the daily activities in the community. As the selected study area comes under village backdrop, implementation of the catchment type RwH structures may improve the ground water table. Figure 2 shows the district wise annual actual and normal rainfall from 01-06-2022 to 29-03-2023 (12).

Figure 2. District wise annual actual and normal rainfall from 01-06-2022 to 29-03-2023

The mean annual rainfall from 01-06-2022 to 29-03-2023 of the state is 968.42 mm. For the selected study area district, average annual rainfall is 1013.1mm as apparent from Fig. 2.

Normally, rainwater is captured from roof catchments, and stored, and it is can be harvested in city’s household buildings, offices, etc., for recharging the ground water table. The roof top area of the campus is figured out to determine the rainwater harvesting potential (13). The catchment area of the selected house is 1306.68 sqft. Table 2 presents the runoff coefficient values for common roofing materials used for construction (14). For the current study, the selected house has been covered with asbestos sheets, which is highlighted in Table 2 whose runoff coefficient is in the range of 0.8 to 0.9.

Table 2. Characteristics features of roof (14)

Type	Typical runoff coefficient	Remarks
GI Sheets	>0.9	Excellent quality water. Surface is smooth and high temperatures help to sterilize bacteria
Tile (glazed)	0.6 – 0.9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good quality water from glazed tiles. • Unglazed can harbor vegetation • Contamination can exist in tile joints
Asbestos Sheets	0.8 – 0.9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New sheets give good quality water • No evidence of carcinogenic effects by ingestion • Slightly porous so reduced runoff coefficient and older roofs harbor moulds and even moss
Organic (Thatch, Cadjan)	0.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor quality water (>200 FC/100ml) • High colouration due to dissolved organic material which does not settle

3. Results and discussion

This study was aimed at surveying selected number of houses within the vicinity of the selected community and few schools to collect information on the selected topic among the public and, students who are ambassadors of the future. Against a question asked whether the public in the community have seen any RwH technique already being implemented, when it was established, in the selected study area, majority of the people (63.9%) replied that they don’t have idea, which paved a way for us to perform research on what is RwH and educate them. Figure 3 shows the result of whether the public in the community have seen any RwH structures already implemented.

Figure 3. Response of the question asked for whether the public in the community have seen any RwH structures already implemented.

Figure 4 shows the result of the question asked for whether the surveyed public is aware of any Governmental byelaws existing for the implementation of RwH structures. Majority of the people (63.9%) replied that they are not aware of any such. It can be inferred that they need a clear understanding on the rules and regulations on this type of information, which can be addressed through awareness campaigns.

Figure 4. Response of the question asked for the idea of any Governmental byelaws are existing for the implementation of RwH structures

Response of the question asked whether the respondents have ever seen RwH structures in any Government offices is shown in Figure 5. Majority of the respondents replied that they have not seen RwH structures implemented in Government offices, indicating that the public and the local government body can be mobilized to think of implementing the RwH structures for future purpose.

Figure 5. Response of the question asked for whether the respondents have ever seen RWH structures in any Government offices

Figure 6 shows the response of the question asked for, which was the first state to make rainwater harvesting compulsory for every building to avoid groundwater depletion. Majority of the respondents replied that they are not aware of any such. Since we have carried out necessary research on this, we have explained them that Tamil Nadu is the first state to make rainwater harvesting compulsory. Respondents response for the question asked for, who can practice the RWH is shown in the Figure 7. Majority of the respondents replied that everyone can practice RWH, indicating that we can mobilize them for the implementation of the RWH structures. Figure 8 shows the response of the respondents for the question asked for, where can be the RWH structures implemented. Majority of the respondents replied that the RWH structures can be implemented in individual houses, apartments, etc., indicating that we can motivate them to implement the RWH structures in their house premises.

Figure 6. Response of the question asked for which was the first state to make RWH compulsory for every building to avoid groundwater depletion

Figure 7. Response for the question asked who can practice the RWH

Figure 8. Response of the respondents for the question where can be the RWH structures implemented

Figure 9 shows the response of the respondents for the question asked whether they have gained sufficient knowledge about RWH to explain it to all. More than 50% of the respondents replied that they can explain, however, they are not confident enough in doing so. It is apparent that, we need to plan for awareness programs to explain them more in detail about the RWH. The response of the respondents for the question asked whether it is important to protect my country's water resources is shown in Figure 10. More than 88% of the respondents agreed and replied that it is very important to protect the country's water resources. It can be inferred that everyone feels that water is one of our resource and we need to safe guard the same. Figure 11 shows the response of the respondents for the question asked whether my personal actions can affect water quality in my county. Nearly 82% of the

respondents replied that their personal actions will affect water quality in my county, indicating that everyone is aware of the significance of the water resources available in the country, hence, we can mobilize them for the implementation of the RwH structures.

Figure 9. Response of the respondents for the question asked whether they have gained sufficient knowledge about RwH to explain it to all

Figure 10. Response of the respondents for the question asked whether it is important to protect my country's water resources

Figure 11. Response of the respondents for the question asked whether my personal actions can affect water quality in my county.

Figure 12 shows the response of the respondents for the question asked for whether my personal actions can affect the availability of water in my county. Nearly 77% of the respondents replied that their personal activities will affect the availability of water in the county, indicating that the community can be mobilized for careful use water resources for daily purposes and incentivize them for the implementation of RWH structures.

Figure 12. Response of the respondents for the question asked for whether my personal actions can affect the availability of water in my county.

Figure 13 shows the response of the respondents for the question asked for whether they have heard or seen water-saving devices been installed in public buildings or government owned facilities. More than 83% of the respondents replied that they have never seen water-saving devices been installed in public buildings or government owned facilities. It is apparent that they are not aware of such and need awareness about the same through awareness programs.

Figure 13. The response of the respondents for the question asked for whether they have heard or seen water-saving devices been installed in public buildings or government owned facilities.

Figure 14 shows the response of the respondents for the question asked for whether they are aware of what is the global water demand that is projected to increase by 2050. Majority of the respondents replied that they are not aware of such information. They were made to understand that global water demand will be projected to increase by 50 to 100 % by 2050.

Figure 14. Response of the respondents for the question asked for whether they are aware of what is the global water demand that is projected to increase by 2050.

A banner was prepared by incorporating the results obtained from the survey to address the above-cited replies of the public in the selected community. Also, few community awareness programs were carried out and showed few case studies of implementation of RwH in several states of India, and made the public aware of the current developments of RwH in tapping the precious resource, i.e., rainwater and conserving the water resources of the country.

Figure 15 shows the time series of rainfall (mm) for the southwest monsoon season for June, July, August and September (JJAS) and annual trends (15). It is apparent that there is a slight increasing trend in the southwest monsoon rainfall, while there is a slight decreasing trend in the annual rainfall. The climatic conditions of Andhra Pradesh have been witnessing variations in their trends in recent times. Kumar et al. (16) reported that mean annual rainfall had an increasing trend in coastal Andhra Pradesh by about 7–9%. Further, Subash et al. (17) while studying the frequency of floods and droughts in the Eastern coastal region of India including Andhra Pradesh found that monsoon rainfall has an increasing trend. Coastal Andhra Pradesh exhibits seasonal variability in rainfall also and maximum rainfall is received in the monsoon season followed by post-monsoon, pre-monsoon and winter seasons (18). Besides, coastal Andhra is expected to witness an increased incidence of extreme climatic events in future (19).

Figure 15. Time series of rainfall (mm) for the southwest monsoon season and annual trends from 1989 to 2018 (30 years). Source: Met Monograph No. ESSO/IMD/HS/Rainfall Variability/01(2020)/25 (15))

Guhathakurta et al. (15), in their study reported the annual mean rainfall map of the Andhra Pradesh state and it shows coastal district of the southern part of the state receives reasonably good amount of rainfall (560-1150 mm). Anantapuram district receives lowest mean rainfall of 558.5 mm annually. It was reported that Guntur, Prakasam, Nellore shows significantly decreasing trend while rest of the districts shows non-significant decreasing trend annually. The decrease in the rainfall in several regions automatically reflects on the groundwater level. For the selected study area district, average annual rainfall is 1013.1mm, which was already shown in Fig. 2.

As per the data available in groundwater year book of 2021-22, Andhra Pradesh, during the pre-monsoon period of Andhra Pradesh, it was observed that annual water level fluctuation has shown a rise in water levels for 75 % of the area. During the post-monsoon, nearly 89% area of the state experienced rise in annual water level fluctuation owing to the excess rainfall in 2021 monsoon. Nearly, 74% of the area experienced rise of water level in decadal mean water level fluctuation of 2011-2020 with respect to May 2021, whereas 83% of the area

experienced rise in decadal mean water level of 2011-2020 with respect to November 2021 (20).

Design of a recharge trench

For the design of a recharge trench, a factor of loose density of the media (void ratio) plays a key role and it has to be applied. The void ratio of the filler material varies with the kind of material used, but for commonly used materials, such as broken bricks, pebbles and gravel, a void ratio of 0.5 may be assumed. From Table 2, runoff coefficient (C) is chosen as 0.85 pertaining to the material used for covering the rooftop. If a large area is considered for RWH structure to recharge the groundwater table, then the type and gradient of ground surface decides the runoff coefficient value (21). Hence, the required capacity of a recharge trench is determined as,

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Rainwater harvesting potential} &= A \times R \times C \\ &= 121.39 \text{ m}^2 \times 1.013 \text{ m (1013.1 mm)} \times 0.85 \\ &= 104.52 \text{ m}^3\end{aligned}$$

A: Catchment area; R: Average annual rainfall; C: runoff coefficient

Assuming a void ratio of 0.5, the required capacity of a recharge tank

$$\begin{aligned}&= 104.52 \text{ m}^3 / 0.5 \\ &= 209 \text{ m}^3\end{aligned}$$

In designing a recharge trench, the length of the trench is an important factor. Once the required capacity is calculated, length can be determined by considering a fixed depth and width.

For depth and width as 2 m and 8 m, respectively, the length is determined as 14 m. Therefore, the recharge trench can be designed for the capacity of 209 m³ or 209, 000 litres (including safety factor) with dimensions of 14m×8m×2m. However, in the present study, as an initiative to mobilize the public for the implementation of RWH, a rainwater recharge pit was prepared in a selected house premises, with the dimensions of 0.5m×0.5m×1.2m

(L×B×D). Figure 16 shows the schematic and the real time photo of the house highlighting the RwGS.

Figure 16. The schematic and the real time photo of the house highlighting the RwGS

Design of a recharge trench in the selected school premises

a. Following details are available:

$$\text{Area of the catchment (A)} = 10.43 \times 8.3 = 89 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{For two rooms} = 178 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{Average annual rainfall (R)} = 1.013 \text{ m (1013.1 mm)}$$

Amount of rainfall that can be harvested from the rooftop:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Annual water harvesting potential} &= 178 \times 1.013 \text{ m (1013.1 mm)} \times 0.85 \\ &= 153.27 \text{ m}^3 \end{aligned}$$

Assuming a void ratio of 0.5, the required capacity of a recharge tank

$$\begin{aligned} &= 153.27 \text{ m}^3 / 0.5 \\ &= 306.53 \text{ m}^3 \end{aligned}$$

As per the information already cited above, for depth and width as 3 m and 8 m, respectively, the length is determined as 12.77 (13) m. Therefore, the recharge trench can be designed for the capacity of 306.53 m³ or 306, 530 litres (including safety factor) with dimensions of 13m×8m×3m. The design along with dos and donts was presented to the school management for the erection of RwGS in the school premises in the near future during renovation period. In a study conducted by Mohammad et al. (22) for the design and implementation of RwH structure, it was reported that harvested rainwater was stored in a soak pit for increasing groundwater table level in the selected study area campus. Anchan and Prasad (1) in their study reported that approximately 1,13,678.9 m³ of storm water can be captured with selected rainwater harvesting system (RWHS) on 19 rooftops of building units.

In general, RwH comprises of installing pipes with a diameter range of 75–100 mm, whereas reinforced cement concrete, precast concrete blocks, brick masonry, stone masonry, etc., are used for the construction. As per the literature available, for sloping roof houses, half-cut PVC pipes can be fitted along the sloping sides to divert the rainwater and the same may be directed to either sump/open wells/bore wells or recharge wells (23). The rainwater that falls can be stored as surface water on the ground, such as ponds or lakes; it can also be stored in tanks build beneath the ground. If the rainwater is left free open, the plants from the soil profile will directly use the same (24). When excess rainfall occur, rainwater percolates through the soil, wherein, some amount will be used by the crops and the remaining part percolates deeper into the soil, which further leads to groundwater recharge (25).

Benefit and cost analysis

Dimensions of recharge trench implemented at a selected house premises in the community are determined as 0.5m×0.5m×1.2m (L×B×D) and this trench is designed and located near to the garden. The trench was back filled with material consisting of pebbles, aggregates, bricks and fine soil. This is more appropriate for small houses and green belt. The total costs including filling material cost is estimated as Rs.5, 000. These designs require very low maintenance and, costs for maintenance and operation will be at lower rates. Dimensions of the recharge trench planned for school are determined as 13m×8m×3m (L×B×D). A simple design was proposed and local materials can be used for the construction. It was advised that use of material comprising of pebbles, aggregates, bricks and fine soil will be more appropriate for the construction. Taking materials cost, work force cost, transportation cost,

and other miscellaneous costs into consideration; total cost for the construction of recharge trench at the school premises is estimated as Rs. 10,000. Table 3 presents the cost estimation for the arrangements of pipeline connecting the recharge pit for the both house and school.

Table 3. The cost estimation for the arrangements of pipeline connecting the recharge pit

S.NO	Name of the object	No. of items required	Cost of each unit [^]	Total
1	10 cm Pipes	10	Rs. 350	350*10= Rs.3500
2	L Bends	10	Rs. 80	80*10= Rs.800
3	Pipe holders	10	Rs. 15	10*15= Rs.150
4	Couples	10	Rs. 12	10*12= Rs.120
	Total			Rs. 4570

[^] Local market price as of March, 2023

The rainwater that enters the groundwater table will recharge the groundwater table, which is an intangible benefit. In general, bottled water in quantity of 20 litres is available in the market at the rate of Rs. 20-30. If a portion of rainwater is diverted to a storage tank and if the water collected in the storage tank is used for drinking and cooking purpose and suppose that one-liter costs one rupee, then the rainwater stored in the tank excluding all losses may result in Rs. 50,000. Therefore, on comparison, payback period for both these structures is less than one year. Anchan and Prasad (1) reported in their study that the payback period is about 13 years for the implementing of RWHS on 19 rooftops of building units.

Conclusion

The concept of rainwater harvesting involves the collection of water from surfaces on which rain falls, and consequently, diverting some portion to groundwater recharge and the other portion for storing the water for future use. Among several methods available for tapping the rainwater, rooftop rainwater harvesting has attained more popularity owing to availability of large rooftop area, ease in the design and maintenance. In this study, an effort was made to carry out an initial field survey to collect data on the status of rainwater harvesting technique implementation pertaining to Pathapadu, Vijayawada Rural, Krishna district, Andhra Pradesh, India. The survey was carried out in 40 houses and one government school, covering

a total of nearly 200 members and 20 students, respectively. It was observed and realized that there is a need to incentivize the public for implementation of RwH technique and, eventually during the time of interaction with public, one of the family has agreed to arrange for a rainwater recharge pit in their house premises. Subsequently, a RwGS was constructed in their house premises with the dimensions of 0.5m×0.5m×1.2m (L×B×D). As apparent from the benefit cost analysis, the implementation of RwGS may lead to a payback period of about one to few years. In view of the scarcity of water in the future, rainwater-harvesting technologies, which are locale specific, can be explored for its practicality and employment in various communities and institutes.

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